

**LINGUO-PRAGMATIC STUDY OF THE TRANSLATION OF UZBEK
FOLK ANECDOTES INTO ENGLISH**

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Annotation: In the thesis, the research of the oral creativity of the peoples of the East is one of the important directions in which comparative folk anecdotes are developing day by day, his activity as a researcher in this regard, the translations of his anecdotes in Uzbek and English, the content of his scientific research , content, structure were discussed.

Keywords: anecdote, linguo-pragmatic study, lexical methodology, pragmatic aspect, metonymy.

Introduction:

Each nation has its own customs, historical characteristics, mentality, and they often become the object of ridicule. Folklore and fairy-tale characters often appear in Russian jokes. Only about Kolobok we came up with a lot of funny stories. For example, the British like to joke about some events in the royal family.

To understand a joke in English, you need not only to know the language, but also to have some idea about the history, culture and lifestyle of the people. Note that the English word "anecdote" itself is not an anecdote, but a joke. Anecdote is translated into Russian as "a short story, an incident from life".

Literature analysis and methodology: English jokes are often based on puns. Therefore, with a literal translation into Russian, such anecdotes do not look funny at all. But those who know the language at a decent level often come up with interesting spoken words themselves. Humor is an invariable part of live communication.

The ability to overcome the situation with a unique sense of humor is even considered a talent in some sense. If you find it difficult to improvise in a foreign language, then you can just try to memorize funny English jokes. Jokes, like aphorisms and quotations, expand the vocabulary and help to understand the characteristics of the national mentality. Therefore, languages are enriched, polished and beautified by borrowing words from each other.

In both directions, the goal is the same, if it is, to study the multiple meanings of words and their methodological possibilities. Studying the multiple meanings of words is primarily for lexical methodology. plays an important role. Because, in order for one word to have different meanings, it is necessary to pay attention to

the stylistic color and meaning of its use in oral and written speech. Like synonymy, homonymy and other lexical tools, 'chish' creates humor, humor, laughter and various puns. In such cases, the original and figurative meaning of the word collide, resulting in an unexpected new meaning.

Results: These subtle shades of meaning of words are widely used as an important descriptive tool in fiction. In our country, favorable conditions and opportunities are being created for the introduction of advanced methods of teaching using modern pedagogical and information and communication technologies, the fundamental improvement of the system of training specialists who have thoroughly mastered foreign languages, and the development of international cooperation in the field. Also, in the process of learning a language, comparing it with one's native language helps to better understand the grammatical side of the newly learned foreign language.

In a two-way comparison of two language systems, the material of each compared language system is compared separately. The characteristic of each unit of the layer is taken into account, the mutual relations of the units of the other layer are taken into account. Comparative typology includes directions such as characterology and universal grammar. However, they have different and similar aspects, and characterology compares only one layer of languages, while universal grammar takes into account lexical tools in addition to grammatical tools when comparing languages.

New ones are being created between years and periods, and the range of meaning of the old ones, which exist in living communication and language, has expanded or narrowed. Even some of them have been forgotten. As proverbs express the conclusion of many centuries of life experiences, constant daily observations in the form of a complete thought in a strict polarity, they are dominated by the diversity of meaning of each word, the stability of expressions, and the stability of form. But depending on the place of use, their range of meaning is constantly expanding.

Discussion:

It is known that stylistics is a branch of linguistics and is a very important aspect in creating humor. Stylistic means of expressiveness should be studied more widely and in detail, because they create a very funny effect and are used more often in humorous texts. The use of the following methodological tools was confirmed during the investigation: epithet, irony, metaphor, metonymy, personification, jargonization, zeugma, litota, oxymoron, amphibole, antithesis, word combination, hyperbole, irony, periphrasis. Humorous texts use the

following stylistic devices more than others: metaphor, metonymy, hyperbole, puns, irony, personification, and oxymoron.

These devices are more common and interesting in the translation of humorous, pragmatic and humorous texts. Comic texts are created based on these means of stylistic expressiveness. As part of our scientific work, we tried to analyze the active stylistic tools of metaphor, metonymy and hyperbole used in Uzbek and English languages.

Linguists approach this transfer of meaning from the point of view of revealing the characteristic features of semes and senses in polysemous words, analysis of events that create transferable meaning, while literary scholars study different means of image in polysemous words are considered to be the factors that create.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, it is permissible to say that it is an emotional-subjective assessment; Identifying linguistic stylistic elements is one of the main problems of literary speech stylistics. This problem is very important in the analysis of comic texts, because emotional effect is a very important aspect in this genre. Not only the Uzbek and English peoples, but also the humorous texts of all nations use more stylistic tools, and this is of great importance in creating humor. Usually the comic function is a distinguishing feature among stylistic devices.

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